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Physics-Informed Neural Network for Building Energy Demand Prediction

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Abstract. The optimization of energy demand in the built environment has become a critical priority in the global drive for sustainability. Despite building energy simulation tools can provide valuable performance insights, their computational demands and complexity often impede practical implementation, especially for small-scale operational.

This study presents the development of a novel surrogate modeling framework designed to predict residential building energy demand while maintaining computational efficiency.

The methodology starts with data generation through EnergyPlus simulations across diverse building configurations, while, for modeling, a physics-informed neural network (PINN) is employed, which integrates domain knowledge from an additional simplified physical model with data-driven predictions. Differently from traditional machine learning approaches, the PINN framework helps to promote thermodynamic consistency by embedding fundamental heat transfer equations and energy conservation principles directly into the learning process, thereby fostering physically meaningful predictions even in scenarios not represented in the training data. The simplified physical model implemented within the loss function is a resistance-capacity model, which captures essential thermal dynamics through a compact representation of heat storage and transfer.

The developed framework tries to effectively fill the gap between high-fidelity simulation tools and practical implementation requirements by enabling accurate and physical-informed evaluation, while accounting for complex system interactions. The PINN's ability to align with physical constraints helps to ensure that the predictions remain reliable even under uncertain or previously unseen conditions, a crucial advantage for real-world applications. Finally, the additional simplified model acts as a physics-informed regularization that is proven to be more effective than common regularization methods in generalizing the model.

1. Introduction

Building energy modeling plays a crucial role in designing energy-efficient buildings, evaluating retrofit strategies, and informing energy policies. Traditional approaches rely on detailed physics-based simulations, which, while accurate, require extensive computational resources and detailed building information, making them impractical for large-scale parametric analyses or real-time optimization tasks [1]. Alternatively, purely data-driven models, while arising as a promising alternative to physics-based modeling, come with their own challenges, particularly when applied to scenarios beyond the training data.

Machine learning methods have been extensively explored as alternatives for building energy analysis [2], learning from simulated or measured data to provide fast approximations of building energy performance. However, they may fail to capture fundamental thermodynamic behavior,

Figure 1. Random building samples

limiting their ability to generalize to unseen conditions.

To address these challenges, physics-informed machine learning has been proposed as a means of integrating physical constraints into data-driven models [3]. Physics-Informed Neural Networks (PINNs) have emerged as a powerful hybrid approach that integrates neural networks with physical constraints derived from established physical laws. Unlike purely data-driven models, PINNs embed physics-based equations directly into the loss function, ensuring that predictions adhere to fundamental principles while exploiting large datasets for learning.

In this paper, a PINN-based framework is introduced for building energy modeling, leveraging a large dataset generated from high-fidelity EnergyPlus simulations. Unlike conventional PINN approaches that incorporate measured data, this work uses a dataset of 25'000 simulated cases spanning a wide range of building configurations and operational conditions. A simplified 2R2C thermal model is integrated into the loss function of the PINN, providing a physics-based regularization mechanism that enhances the generalization of the model (e.g. [6]). The proposed approach addresses the following key challenges:

- (i) Leveraging high-fidelity EnergyPlus simulations to train a PINN while integrating a reduced-order thermal model (2R2C) for physics-based regularization;
- (ii) Ensuring the simplified thermal model captures essential building physics while maintaining computational efficiency;
- (iii) Incorporating operational schedules and weather data into the modeling framework to improve robustness;
- (iv) Achieving accurate energy demand predictions without requiring detailed real-world data.

2. Methodology

2.1. Dataset Generation

A dataset consisting of 25'000 samples has been generated using EnergyPlus simulations to capture different thermal behaviors of residential buildings under diverse parametric variations. The dataset covers a wide range of inputs which have been systematically randomized to ensure a representative distribution of building typologies and energy performance characteristics.

In particular, the building geometry has been generated through an algorithm that defines floor plan vertices by creating randomized rectangular segments and adjusting them to maintain realistic architectural configurations (Figure 1). The final layouts have been processed to ensure geometric consistency and proper alignment of walls. The number of floors varies randomly from 1 to 6, with floor heights between 3.0 m and 3.4 m. The Energy Reference Area (ERA) is constrained within a range of 120–400 m². The thermal transmittance (*U-value*) of walls spans from 0.2 to 1.5 W/m²K, while that of roofs and floors ranges from 0.15 to 1.0 W/m²K and 0.25 to 1.5 W/m²K, respectively [5]. Window glazing properties have been defined with

solar transmittance values that are calibrated to vary with the randomized U -value, ensuring consistency in optical and thermal behavior.

Regarding operational parameters, the simulations incorporate randomized schedules for internal heat gains due to occupancy and electrical equipment, considering typical residential usage patterns. Occupant schedules follow weekday and weekend variations, with fractional presence values ranging from 0.1 (unoccupied hours) to 1 (peak occupancy). Equipment schedules vary in a similar manner, with power consumption per occupant ranging between 70–120 W.

Building orientation is also randomly assigned with azimuth angles among predefined values (e.g. 0° , 20° , 45° , 80°), capturing diverse solar exposure scenarios. The window-to-wall ratio (WWR) varies from 10% to 30%, influencing both solar gains and infiltration rates. Adjacent buildings are accounted for by defining adiabatic walls, with 0 to 2 facades randomly selected as shared boundaries.

Infiltration rates are dynamically adjusted based on the WWR, with baseline values set at 0.5 air changes per hour (ACH). These rates are further modulated through daily schedules that simulate natural ventilation effects, such as reduced airflow during peak summer hours and increased rates overnight.

Each building configuration is simulated in EnergyPlus with a timestep resolution of 15 minutes. The simulations are driven by real weather data corresponding to four cities in the Ticino region in Switzerland (Mendrisio, Lugano, Bellinzona, Locarno). Ground temperatures are included to model conductive heat transfer through floors accurately.

The final dataset includes key output variables obtained from the simulations such as: indoor air temperature profiles ($^\circ\text{C}$) per zone; heating energy demands (kWh/m^2 ERA) per month and annually; number of hours per day with indoor temperatures ($^\circ\text{C}$) and relative humidity (%) outside acceptable ranges.

2.2. Reduced-Order Thermal Model: 2R2C

To represent the thermal dynamics of the building envelope, a simplified 2R2C (two-resistor, two-capacitor) lumped-parameter model has been adopted. This model approximates the heat transfer mechanisms through the building envelope and indoor air by considering thermal resistances and capacitances.

The 2R2C model consists of two thermal resistances (R_1 and R_2) and two thermal capacitances (C_1 and C_2), representing:

- R_1 : Thermal resistance of the building envelope;
- R_2 : Thermal resistance between the internal mass and the indoor air;
- C_1 : Thermal capacitance of the building envelope, accounting for its thermal inertia;
- C_2 : Thermal capacitance of the indoor air.

The system is governed by two differential equations derived from the lumped heat balance:

$$C_1 \frac{dT_m}{dt} = \frac{T_{\text{ext}} - T_m}{R_1} + \frac{T_{\text{air}} - T_m}{R_2} + Q_{\text{int,mass}} + Q_{\text{sol,mass}} \quad (1)$$

$$C_2 \frac{dT_{\text{air}}}{dt} = \frac{T_m - T_{\text{air}}}{R_2} + Q_{\text{inf}} + Q_{\text{int,air}} + Q_{\text{sol,air}} + Q_{\text{heating}} \quad (2)$$

where T_{air} , T_m , T_{ext} are temperatures of indoor air, building mass and outdoor air, while Q_{inf} , Q_{int} , Q_{sol} represent heat flows from infiltration, internal gains and solar gains. Q_{heating} is the heat provided by the heating system that is used to estimate the losses.

The values of R_1 , R_2 , C_1 , and C_2 are directly derived from the building properties set in the EnergyPlus simulation. The thermal resistances are computed as follows:

$$R_1 = \left(\sum_i U_i A_i \right)^{-1} \quad R_2 = \frac{1}{h_{\text{conv}} A_{\text{int}}} \quad (3)$$

where U_i is the thermal transmittance ($\text{W}/\text{m}^2\text{K}$) of the i -th building element (walls, roof, floor), A_i is its corresponding surface area, and h_{conv} is the internal convective heat transfer coefficient. The capacitances are computed considering the thermal mass of the envelope and indoor air volume:

$$C_1 = \sum_i \rho_i c_{p,i} V_i \quad C_2 = \rho_{\text{air}} c_{p,\text{air}} V_{\text{air}} \quad (4)$$

where ρ_i and $c_{p,i}$ are the density and specific heat capacity of the building materials, V_i is their volume, and V_{air} is the indoor air volume.

These parameters are set based on the specific building configuration from the EnergyPlus simulation, ensuring consistency between the reduced-order model and the high-fidelity dynamic simulation.

2.3. Physics-Informed Neural Network

The neural network consists of multiple fully connected layers with nonlinear activation functions, mapping the 21 input features to the target monthly energy demand. The inputs to the network include geometric features (e.g. shape factor, number of floors, heated area); envelope properties (e.g. window-to-wall ratio, shading factor, thermal transmittance); thermal mass parameters (e.g. air capacity multiplier); operational conditions (e.g. setpoint temperatures) and environmental factors (e.g. building orientation and city location).

The model mainly predicts monthly energy demand per unit area, plus additional statistics on indoor temperature and humidity. The PINN is trained by minimizing a composite loss function (Figure 2) that includes both data-driven and physics-based terms:

$$\mathcal{L} = \lambda_d \mathcal{L}_{\text{data}} + \lambda_p \mathcal{L}_{\text{phys}} \quad (5)$$

where λ_d and λ_p are assumed to be equal to 0.7 and 0.3 respectively. $\mathcal{L}_{\text{data}}$ measures the discrepancy between network predictions (E_{pred}) and EnergyPlus simulation outputs (E_{sim}) using mean squared error (MSE), while $\mathcal{L}_{\text{phys}}$ enforces compliance with the governing thermal equations by penalizing deviations from the 2R2C-based energy balance:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{data}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (E_{\text{pred},i} - E_{\text{sim},i})^2 \quad \mathcal{L}_{\text{phys}} = \alpha_1 \mathcal{L}_{\text{RC}} + \alpha_2 \mathcal{L}_{\text{annual}} \quad (6)$$

The physics loss includes multiple terms like \mathcal{L}_{RC} that ensures consistency between the PINN predictions and the physically derived reduced-order model, and $\mathcal{L}_{\text{annual}}$ that controls energy conservation over a year by enforcing consistency between annual and monthly demand. In particular:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{RC}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (E_{\text{RC},i} - E_{\text{pred},i})^2 \quad \mathcal{L}_{\text{annual}} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(E_{\text{annual}}^{\text{pred}} - \sum_{m=1}^{12} E_{\text{pred},m} \right)^2 \quad (7)$$

E_{RC} represents the monthly energy demand calculated via the 2R2C model, including factors such as envelope thermal transmittance, infiltration, internal gains, and shading.

The coefficients α_1, α_2 are used to balance the contribution of each physical constraint, assumed equal to 0.7 and 0.3, respectively.

Figure 2. PINN framework scheme

3. Results

To evaluate the effectiveness of physics-informed regularization, 300 additional artificial observations have been generated to explore domains distinct from those in the original training dataset, introducing more diverse and challenging conditions by modifying key input parameters. Specifically, the range of *U-values* for the envelope has been extended to incorporate more extreme boundary conditions, while building geometries have been diversified to include more complex architectural configurations. Thermal inertia values have been increased to evaluate the model’s capacity to capture long-term thermal dynamics, and the ERA range has been significantly expanded to test its adaptability to varying spatial characteristics.

A comparative analysis has been conducted against a classic neural network with an identical architecture, differing only in the loss function used during training. To ensure reproducibility and mitigate potential biases introduced by random initialization, a fixed random seed has been employed for weight initialization in both models.

Results shows the PINN’s ability to extrapolate beyond the training domain while maintaining an acceptable predictive accuracy under diverse and challenging conditions (Table 1 and Figure 3). The moderate *R*² values (0.68 & 0.63) are partly due to the increased diversity of the test

Table 1. Performance metrics comparison between PINN and ANN on the new test dataset.

Metric	PINN	ANN	Improvement (%)
MSE	0.53	0.63	14.7
RMSE	0.73	0.79	7.7
MAE	0.45	0.48	7.3
R ²	0.68	0.63	7.9

dataset compared to the training domain, but also to the absence of certain input variabilities in the training data (e.g. per-person energy consumption of appliances), not explicitly incorporated into the model calibration process. Finally, the network architectures have not been properly optimized, which may also have contributed to the observed performance limitations. However,

Figure 3. [a] Mean percentage error per cold month, on the new test dataset. [b] Predicted vs. actual energy demand using PINN (left) and classical ANN (right) evaluated on the same dataset.

these factors do not compromise the validity of the comparison between the PINN and the standard ANN, as both models are equally affected.

4. Conclusions

The proposed PINN architecture has been trained considering key building and environmental parameters. The physics-informed approach enables seamless integration of high-fidelity EnergyPlus simulations (or data if available) with computationally efficient reduced-order models, effectively leveraging the strengths of both modeling paradigms.

Unlike standard methods (e.g., L1 or L2 norms) that impose arbitrary constraints on model parameters, physics-based regularization seeks that predictions satisfy fundamental thermodynamic principles even when extrapolating beyond the training data domain. In general, by constraining the solution space to physically plausible regions, the PINN can demonstrate higher generalization capabilities when applied to building configurations with geometric and material properties that differ from those in the training dataset. This robustness against input distribution shifts is particularly valuable in building energy modeling applications.

Future research directions include expansion to incorporate renewable energy systems and storage technologies, enhancing applicability in emerging smart grid architectures and enabling seamless integration with distributed energy resources and advanced load management strategies.

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References

- [1] Clarke, J. A., "Energy simulation in building design" Routledge, 2001.
- [2] Amasyali, K., & El-Gohary, N. M., "A review of data-driven building energy consumption prediction studies" *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, vol. 81, pp. 1192-1205, 2018.
- [3] Raissi, M., Perdikaris, P., & Karniadakis, G. E., "Physics-informed neural networks: A deep learning framework for solving forward and inverse problems involving nonlinear partial differential equations." *Journal of Computational Physics*, vol. 378, pp. 686-707, 2019.

- [4] Wang, Z., Hong, T., & Piette, M. A., “Building thermal load prediction through shallow machine learning and deep learning” *Applied Energy*, vol. 263, 114683, 2020.
- [5] Wang, D., Landolt, J., Mavromatidis, G., Orehounig, K., & Carmeliet, J. (2018). “CESAR: A bottom-up building stock modelling tool for Switzerland to address sustainable energy transformation strategies.” *Energy and Buildings*, 169, 9-26.
- [6] Karniadakis, G. E., Kevrekidis, I. G., Lu, L., Perdikaris, P., Wang, S., & Yang, L. (2021). *Physics-informed machine learning*. *Nature Reviews Physics*, 3(6), 422-440.